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*ЭКСПЕРТ – ЭТО ЧЕЛОВЕК, КОТОРЫЙ
СОВЕРШИЛ ВСЕ ВОЗМОЖНЫЕ ОШИБКИ
В ОЧЕНЬ УЗКОЙ СПЕЦИАЛЬНОСТИ.*

Нильс Бор

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FACTORS AFFECTING HUMAN ALIENATION IN THE INFORMATION SOCIETY

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Abstract: The article presents a scientific and philosophical analysis of the impact of globalization and the acceleration of information flows on the spiritual and moral life of people, the emergence of alienation as a social evil. It is argued that in the fight against it, it is necessary to strengthen philosophical education based on national values.

Keywords: alienation, information society, coherence, philosophical sciences, independent thinking skills, healthy worldview, cultural approach, thought, social person.

INTRODUCTION

The further rapid development of science as a social institution requires special attention to all factors affecting it. Indeed, I.A.Karimov did not in vain emphasize that, "...in the current age of information, communication and computer technologies, when the Internet is increasingly penetrating all aspects of our lives, and the struggle for people's minds and thinking is gaining decisive importance, there is no need to talk about how urgent and priority these issues are for our society» [1]. Thus, the development of society is increasingly associated with informatization and forms a large research universe. Information is an important factor in socio-economic, technological

and cultural development. Its importance in the life of society is increasing day by day. In modern society, human production activities take place within the framework of generalized production. Generalized production consists of inextricably linked physical (material) and informational-logical parts. It is known that countries that have given strength to the information-logical part of production have achieved high productivity and the production of modern, marketable products. The basis of the resources of information-logical production is information, and the means of labor are computing equipment, its software, information technologies, etc. The concepts of information and informatization have become one of the most important areas of modern science, determining the trend of social development.

Although the concept of an information society has been studied by scientists and specialists for many years, they have studied the information society from one perspective: either from an economic, technical, social or cultural point of view. The complexity, versatility, breadth of possible areas of application, and rapid development of information are reflected in constantly new approaches to the concepts of «information» and «information technologies». Therefore, the concept of information ranges from the most general philosophical definition, such as «information is a reflection of the real world» [2], to the narrowest definition, such as «information is all the information that objects can store» [3]. The simplest classical definition of information is information. According to N. Wiener, «Information is the expression of the content received from the external world in the process of getting used to it». Here, information is expressed as a reflection of the external world (epistemological aspect) and adaptation (adaptation to it). L. Popov considers «Information as the elimination of ambiguity in the process of communication and communication» [4]. This definition mainly focuses on the philosophical, psychological (communication, connection) side of information. R. Ashby also defines it as «Information is the norm of structures, novelty, originality» [5]. L.G. Svitich understands it as «The concept of information has many meanings, but in a general philosophical, metalinguistic sense it is a set of potential, broadly illuminated real essences» [6]. These ideas indicate that different specialists approach the concept of information from the perspective of their specialization. Different approaches to the concept of information are associated with the existence of two completely opposite attributive and functional concepts in science since the 70s of the 20th century. In our opinion, the attributive approach considers information as a property of matter, while the functional approach associates it with the activity of self-organizing and organized systems. A.D. Ursul defined it as «Information is a reflection of diversity» [7]. Later, he explains his concept of information as a complement to diversity and a part of the reflecting side of information. In our opinion, this definition is not sufficient for understanding

in classical and post-classical methodology. N.A.Shermuhamedova divides information into social and scientific types of information [8]. Indeed, social information in social management is the coordination of various processes. M.N.Abdullaeva, A.F.Fayzullayev, R.Imomaliyeva, Z. Davronov, K. Tulenova analyzed the epistemological aspects of informatization [9], while M.A.Usmanova, O.A.Lanseva, and A.K.Turashbekova [10] analyzed the role of socio-political and spiritual factors in the development of an information society in their scientific and research works.

Scientists have different opinions about the information society. For example, Japanese scientists believe that the computerization process in the information society will allow people to use a reliable source of information, to ensure a high level of automation of information processing in production and social spheres. And the driving force in the development of society should be information production, not material products.

In an information society, not only production, but also the entire lifestyle and value system changes. In contrast to an industrial society, where all activities are directed towards the production and consumption of goods, in an information society, intelligence and knowledge are produced and consumed, which leads to an increase in the share of mental labor. A person is required to have the ability to be creative, and the need for knowledge increases.

The material and technological basis of the information society is formed by various systems based on computer technology and computer networks, information technologies, and telecommunications.

An information society is a society in which most members of society are engaged in the production, storage, processing, and dissemination of information, especially its highest form, knowledge.

In the transition to an information society, a new information processing industry is emerging based on computer and telecommunications information technologies.

It is now clear that in order for a country to take its rightful place in the 21st century and compete equally with other countries in economic competition, it must restructure its economic structure, priorities, wealth, institutions, and adapt its industry to the requirements of information systems.

Alienation is primarily accompanied by a decrease in the level of intimate communication between members of society. In an information society, the increasing takeover of a large part of human tasks by technology, the lack or complete absence of the skills to acquire new information using these technologies, and the need to use them in the right places, lead to a person becoming strongly attached to this information and technology, and a growing sense of indifference towards their loved ones.

The issue of informatization of society is reflected in two main theoretical and methodological approaches of scientists:

— the technocratic approach reflects the use of information technologies in the production and management spheres as a means of increasing production efficiency. — the humanitarian approach emphasizes that information technologies are used not only in production, but also in an important part of human life — the social sphere. It is from the point of view of these approaches that the concept of informatization requires, first of all, the creation of a large-scale system of structured information technologies, encompassing the tasks of searching, collecting, storing, processing and providing activities with information.

The following types of alienation can be distinguished in modern society:

1. Economic. 2. Political. 3. Cultural. 4. Social. 5. Spiritual.

These types of alienation have their own specific forms. For example, economic alienation has three forms:

alienation from activity;

alienation from management of activities;

alienation from the results of activity.

Political alienation consists of alienation from political authority (absenteeism) [11]; cultural alienation consists of alienation from communication, from people to each other; and psychological alienation consists of alienation from oneself. The process of alienation and decline are interdependent phenomena. If the rate of production in a society sharply decreases, economic relations are broken, the value of money decreases, prices increase rapidly, management structures are disrupted, and political tensions arise, we can assume that all spheres of society have fallen into decline. It is clear that this deep decline negatively affects the world of strong alienation of people, leading to the formation of certain, i.e., orderly, orderly, etc. In turn, the more the process of alienation expands, the deeper the decline becomes. For example, in the production process, a division of labor occurs. This is a huge step towards progress. But at the same time, a type of social relations based on social ownership — production relations — is formed, on the basis of which the direct producer is alienated from the means of production and gradually becomes alienated as a result of his labor. Now the product of labor is of no interest to this producer. According to the teachings of Marxism, after private property was socialized, the means of production should now be owned jointly by the direct producers. But in social practice, the opposite turned out to be the case. The proletariat, having seized political power, turned the means of production into state property. According to the logic of the socialist revolution, these measures should have struck at the root of the alienation process. But the social property that we have been taught for 70 years of history was state property. And this property turned out to be the most disgusting, unjust type of private property. Because state property does not have a real owner. It was an abstract concept. And the working person was again alienated

from property. State property, however, became the private property of the state apparatus, transforming this nomenclature into a «new» class. As a result of these negative processes, production could not find its true owner.

On the political front, many members of society were also alienated from political power. That is, although political power was declared to be the power of the people, the power of the whole people, in reality it became the private property of a certain group — the elite. On this basis, an entire people became alienated from the political power of the state, and a huge chasm appeared between this alienated masses and the nomenclature. In turn, these processes led to political collapse, and because of this collapse, countries with totalitarian regimes that could not be defeated by an external enemy disintegrated on their own.

Alienation in the cultural sphere has also caused a spiritual decline that has very deep negative consequences. The role of spirituality and culture in creating a healthy environment in society is unique. Because they have a great impact on the harmonious formation of individuals. If members of society move away from their spirituality, rich cultural heritage and become alienated from it, they will begin to deny everything from their origins to the national customs and traditions of their nations. If we turn to our recent past, to its living, we will see clear evidence of these lines. For example, our alienation from our rich cultural heritage has turned us, as the famous writer Chingiz Aitmatov put it, into *mankurts*, that is, we have become distant from the history of our people, national liberation movements and their leaders, our religion and identity. Having achieved independence, our state began to eliminate cultural alienation. The ideological vacuum in the minds of members of society, the fruit of the cultural policy of the 70-year period of dependence — the state of the ideological gap between the emergence of a new ideology in place of the communist ideology — especially created the basis for the further development of the alienation process. Our national idea, the «Uzbek Model of Development» and today's «Strategy of Actions» program are acting as a practical tool in eliminating the problem of human alienation. A spiritually and morally mature person acts as the driving force of society. Touching upon this issue, I. Karimov emphasized: «The fate of development is decided by spiritually mature personnel. Technical knowledge, the ability to master complex technology must go hand in hand with spiritual perfection, independent thinking. Intellectual intelligence and spiritual and moral potential are the two wings of an enlightened person» [12].

Social alienation, which is considered an important alienation in sociology, occurs as a result of people moving away from communication and from each other. A person, by his very nature, has a social nature. People always communicate with each other in relationships based on the needs that arise due to interaction. The social meaning of communication is that it serves as

a means of transmitting cultural forms and social experiences. However, the economic downturn puts many people in a difficult economic situation. As a result, it is difficult for most members of society to get used to the relations of a market economy. As a result, the restriction and normalization of the system of needs during inflation leads to the formation of aggressiveness, ignorance in people, and the loss of traditions and customs, spiritual values in citizens. Such negative factors increase the alienation of people from each other and an informal law appears that everyone should do as they please. The pitiful state of affairs is demonstrated by the following true thoughts of one of the famous philosophers, quoted in the work «High spirituality is an invincible force»: «Do not be afraid of enemies — they can kill you if you go anywhere. Do not be afraid of friends — they can betray you if you go anywhere. Fear indifferent people — they will neither kill you nor betray you, but only because of their silent and indifferent look, betrayals and murders occur on earth» [13].

Spiritual alienation is a person's alienation from his own essence. This problem was very well developed by the German thinker E. Fromm. According to him, each level of human alienation from himself, under the influence of a social structure that is always hostile to the human essence, is characterized by a certain social character — worldliness, exploitativeness, receptiveness (pattern, mold), market orientation.

E. Fromm describes modern society as a product of the level of alienation resulting from the processes of «machineization», «computerization» and «robotization» of human essence. [14] A social movement based on a market economy has emerged, in which the desire for consumption, feelings of indecision, isolation and other negative states and emotions take on central importance.

Here, one can see that psychological and social alienation are very closely intertwined. When people become alienated from each other in relationships and communication, they also become alienated from themselves, because as a result of alienation from each other, they can become isolated, bored, and lose interest in life. As a result, a person loses confidence in his future, his dreams, and he considers himself an outsider, and this process often leads to negative consequences. Such negative consequences can range from decreased productivity to helplessness in the face of a minor problem and even suicide.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, only if the various processes of alienation in today's society are eliminated as soon as possible on the basis of science and harmony, will society develop in a healthy environment and negative social phenomena be eliminated in a timely manner. For example, to eliminate alienation from work, it is necessary, first of all, to make people interested in the results of their labor and, as a result, to radically change their attitude towards work and organize them to work with interest and energy.

It is also very important to eliminate the problem of alienation from production management. This requires liberalizing production relations, improving existing management systems in enterprises, organizations and institutions through democratic means, and assigning workers and employees specific tasks and responsibilities of the owner of the enterprise.

To eliminate cultural alienation, it is necessary to improve the attitude towards cultural heritage, ensure that every member of society is well aware of spiritual values, and ensure that sufficient funds are allocated for cultural construction.

To eliminate social alienation, people's relationships with each other and their problems must be built on the basis of true solidarity and care, so that each person can sincerely feel that they are needed by others.

Measures to eliminate spiritual alienation are an integral continuation of the elimination of social alienation. Only when a person can feel spiritually that he is needed by someone, he will never fall into despair. He will be freed from the danger of isolation and suffering, and as a result, there will be no reason for him to become alienated from himself, from his essence.

The new society we are building is steadily overcoming current difficulties in order to overcome alienation processes more quickly and achieve real development, freedom, and liberation. There is every reason to hope that the results of these efforts will certainly emerge in the coming years.

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